

1 NECTIN4 marks the TE.

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 Nectin-4 as a lineage commitment reporter during a key developmental transition in embryonic stem cells
10 of the human embryo.

11 Citations

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13 1. Reymond, N., Fabre, S., Lecocq, E., Adelaide, J., Dubreuil, P. and Lopez, M., 2001.
14 Nectin4/PRR4, a new afadin-associated member of the nectin family that trans-interacts with
15 nectin1/PRR1 through V domain interaction. Journal of Biological Chemistry, 276(46), pp.43205-43215.
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